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Original article

Microwave Reaction Improved Heterocyclization of Quinazolinone Ring in Synthesis of Erlotinib Analogues

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Sha Li and Jie Jiang conceived the idea, designed and supervised the research. Jianghong Man and Jianbin Qi performed the research, collected data, conducted the analysis and wrote the paper. All authors contributed to the writing and revisions.

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Core tip:

Drug resistance caused by point mutations in epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) weakened therapeutic efficacy of EGFR inhibitors of tinibs. Thus, the discovery of new tinib analogues of greater efficacy was an attractive focus. As an important intermediate of nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds with diverse chemical reactivity and a wide range of biological activity, quinazoline was regarded as an important fragment of tinib analogues. Thus, the synthesis of quinazolinone intermediates was a key step which would limit the overall yield of tinib analogues. Based on this situation, a simple one-pot microwave reaction was adopted to improve synthesis of 6,7-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)quinazolin-4(3H)-one, the important fragment in erlotinib analogues. By screening the microwave power, temperature and time of reaction, a relatively satisfactory yield of 50% was achieved under appropriate reaction condition. The results were favorable to increase the overall yield in synthesis of erlotinib analogues as well as provided valuable reference to synthesis of other quinazolinone derivatives.

Abstract:

Background Tinibs were a kind of important epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) inhibitors used as potential therapeutic agents in treating non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) in clinic. The drug resistance of clinical used tinibs made the development of more active tinib analogues an attractive field in research. Quinazoline ring was regarded as the key fragment in tinibs and quinazolinone was indispensable intermediate in the synthesis of quinazoline. Thus, synthesis of quinazolinone intermediates was a key step which would further limit the overall yield of final product of tinib analogues. However, the commonly used synthetic

scheme was somewhat complicated and time consuming with relatively low yield in heterocyclization of quinazolinone and its derivatives.

Aim In this work, we intended to explore an effective way to improve synthesis of heterocyclization of 6,7-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (compound 5), the key fragment of erlotinib analogues, in both reaction procedure and yield, thus to provide reference to synthesis of other quinazolinone derivatives.

Methods A simple microwave-assisted one-pot reaction was employed to improve the synthesis of heterocyclization of quinazolinone ring. The reaction conditions, including microwave power, temperature and time of reaction, were screened to achieve high yield under simple operation.

Results 6,7-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (compound 5) was successfully synthesized from starting material of 4,5-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)-2-nitrobenzotrile by microwave reaction, which was finished in 1 hour just by one step. The yield of heterocyclization was increased from 29.8% of commonly used three-step scheme to 50% herein.

Conclusion Microwave reaction efficiently improved synthesis of heterocyclization of 6,7-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)quinazolin-4(3H)-one into "quinazolinone in both synthetic procedure and yield. The results may provide valuable reference to synthesis of other quinazolinone derivatives.

Key words Quinazolinone; heterocyclization; microwave reaction.

INTRODUCTION

At present, a variety of EGFR inhibitors of tinibs were effectively used therapy of NSCLC, such as gefitinib¹, erlotinib², icotinib³, afatinib, canertinib, vandetanib, dacomitinib and so on. However, acquired point mutations in EGFR gene, especially for T790M mutation, were commonly observed in many NSCLC cases⁴, which led to drug resistance and weakened therapeutic efficacy of tinibs^{5,6}. Therefore, development of novel tinib analogues of better activity was an attractive point.

Figure 1 Chemical structure of some effective EGFR inhibitors of tinibs.

The tinib drugs were reported to achieve antitumor effect by the quinazolinone core ring binding to a hydrophobic pocket at the N-terminus of EGFR binding region⁷⁻⁹, indicating quinazolinone to be the chief scaffold (Fig. 1). In most of the synthetic routes of these tinibs, the formation of quinazolinone intermediate was an indispensable part which thus was a key step related to the overall yield of final product. Commonly, to synthesize quinazolinone, substituted benzonitrile was used as a raw material, the reaction required at least two steps, and the reaction yield was about 8% to 30%^{10,11}. Some researchers put efforts to enhance the yield in the synthesis of quinazolinone intermediate. Kundu *et al.*¹², for example, got the quinazolinone intermediates by one-pot reductive cyclization in preparing antitumor quinazolinone precursors, while Saari *et al.*¹³ efficiently converted 2-aminobenzotrile into quinazolin-4(3H)-one under microwave irradiation within a short time.

In order to develop new tinib analogues of greater efficacy, we selected 6,7-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)quinazolin-4(3H)-one part of erlotinib as basic structure for modification. The two 2-methoxyethoxyl chains were somewhat bulky substituent groups which might affect the reaction efficiency of heterocyclization of quinazolinone ring. By using the commonly used three-step reaction, the heterocyclization yield was 29.8%, which further affected the overall

yield. To expect higher yield and optimal reaction route and condition, in this work, we tried one-pot microwave reaction and screened the reaction conditions to figure out its possible advantage in cyclization of quinazolinones.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Hydroxylamine hydrochloride, indium trichloride, formamide, sodium formate dehydrate, dichloromethane (DCM), petroleum ether (PE), ethyl acetate (EA), methanol, tetrahydrofuran (THF), acetonitrile, formic acid, trimethylamine (TEA), glacial acetic acid, chloroform, nitric acid, potassium carbonate and *p*-Toluenesulfonyl chloride (TsCl) were reagent grade and commercially available.

Thin-layer chromatography plates of silica gel 254F were purchased from Merck. CDCl_3 or DMSO-d_6 was used to dissolve chemicals for $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra determination at room temperature on a Bruker AV-300 spectrometer, and the spectra were reported in chemical shifts δ (ppm) relative to tetramethylsilane (δ 0.0 ppm). Positive-ion electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectra were recorded on a Finnigan LCQ Advantage MAX mass spectrometer (4000 Q TRAP) of Applied Biosystems.

EXPERIMENTAL

In this work, 6,7-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)quinazolin-4(3*H*)-one of erlotinib (compound 5) was synthesized according to **Scheme 1**. Taking ethylene glycol monomethyl ether as starting material, compound 1 was prepared by nucleophilic substitution with TsCl in THF. In case of nitrogen protection, 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde was reacted with 2-methoxyethyl-4-methylbenzenesulfonate in acetonitrile to generate 3,4-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)benzaldehyde, compound 2. The aldehyde group of compound 2 was reduced by $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ to yield 3,4-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)benzoxonitrile (compound 3) followed by a nitration reaction to obtain 4,5-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)-2-nitrobenzoxonitrile, compound 4. Finally, InCl_3 was used as a catalyst to enable compound 4 cyclized in formamide to yield compound 5 by microwave-assisted one-pot reaction.

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions: (I) TsCl, THF, NaOH, H_2O , ice-bath, 6 h; (II) acetonitrile, K_2CO_3 , N_2 protection, 84°C , 36 h; (III) $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$, HCOONa , HCOOH , 85°C , 5 h; (IV) 65% HNO_3 , CH_3COOH , ice-bath/4 h, 50°C /4 h; (V) HCONH_2 , InCl_3 , MW/400W, 110°C , 1 h.

2-methoxyethyl-4-methylbenzenesulfonate (1)

Ethylene glycol monomethyl ether (2.28 g, 30 mmol) and Sodium hydroxide (1.44 g, 36 mmol) were added into a mixture of THF and water, and treated with ice bath. After 2 hours, TsCl (5.99g, 31.5 mmol) dissolved in THF was added dropwise to the above system under ice bath. After a reaction of 4 h, THF was removed and the residue was extracted with DCM after washed with brine. After dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , the solvent of organic layer was evaporated under reduced pressure, and the residue was separated on silica gel column by a mixture of PE:EA (9:1, v/v). After solvent evaporation, oily compound 1 was yield. (3.24 g, 47 ESI-MS m/z : 231.0 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, 248.3 $[\text{M}+\text{NH}_4]^+$. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, DMSO-d_6): δ 7.79 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 2H), 7.48 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 4.16-4.08 (m, 2H), 3.55-3.44 (m, 2H), 3.18 (s, 3H), 2.41 (s, 3H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, DMSO-d_6): δ 145.37, 132.85, 130.57, 128.06, 70.17, 69.71, 58.37, 21.50.

3,4-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)benzaldehyde (2)

To a solution of 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (6.9 g, 50 mmol) in acetonitrile, compound 1 (23.1 g, 100 mmol) and K_2CO_3 (13.8 g, 100 mmol) was added followed by evacuating air, and then the mixture was heated to 84 °C and reacted for 36 h under N_2 protection. The reaction mixture was filtered and then acetonitrile in filtrate was removed. After brine washing, EA extraction, anhydrous Na_2SO_4 drying, and concentration in turn, the residue was separated on silica gel column by a mixture of PE:EA (4:1, v/v). The eluent was vacuum evaporated to obtain compound 2 as orange oil (20.4 g, 80.3%). ESI-MS m/z : 255.3 $[M+H]^+$, 277.3 $[M+Na]^+$. 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 9.79 (s, 1H), 7.40 (dt, $J = 8.2, 2.6, 1.8$ Hz, 2H), 6.96 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.23-4.13 (m, 4H), 3.76 (dt, $J = 6.2, 3.8$ Hz, 4H), 3.41 (s, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 190.90, 154.35, 149.16, 130.20, 126.75, 112.43, 111.70, 70.76, 70.66, 68.57, 68.55, 59.27, 59.19.

3,4-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)benzointrile (3)

Sodium formate (2.68 g, 39.9 mmol) in formic acid (1.63 g, 35.4 mmol) was added with compound 2 (5.0 g, 19.69 mmol), heated to 85 °C, and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3.3 g, 47.2 mmol) was then added to react for 5 hours. After cooled down to room temperature, cold brine was added into the reaction mixture under stirring, and a large amount of into precipitate generated. After filtration, the crude product was further recrystallized using EA to yield white solid compound 3 (3.7 g, 75.5%). ESI-MS m/z : 252.3 $[M+H]^+$, 269.3 $[M+NH_4]^+$. 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 7.27 (dd, $J = 8.4, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.15 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 6.93 (dd, $J = 8.4, 2.7$ Hz, 1H), 4.25-4.13 (m, 4H), 3.79 (dt, $J = 4.3, 3.1$ Hz, 4H), 3.45 (d, $J = 0.9$ Hz, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 152.93, 148.90, 126.83, 119.16, 117.05, 113.51, 104.17, 70.80, 70.69, 69.05, 68.62, 59.29, 59.25.

4,5-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)-2-nitrobenzointrile (4)

The solution of compound 3 (3.7 g, 14.8 mmol) in glacial acetic acid was added dropwise into HNO_3 (65%) pre-cooled at 0 °C, and the mixture was reacted 4 h at 0 °C followed by another 4 h at 50 °C. Then ice water and precipitate generated. After filtration and washed with ice water and then n-hexane, the filter cake was dried and compound 4 of yellow solid was yielded (2.2 g, 50%). ESI-MS m/z : 297.3 $[M+H]^+$. 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 7.87 (s, 1H), 7.29 (s, 1H), 4.31 (td, $J = 6.2, 4.6$ Hz, 4H), 3.88-3.79 (m, 4H), 3.47 (s, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 153.16, 151.90, 142.69, 117.32, 115.55, 109.62, 100.85, 70.51, 70.45, 69.61, 69.42, 59.38.

6,7-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (5)

After dissolving compound 4 (0.4 g, 1.35 mmol) and $InCl_3$ (0.3 g, 1.35 mmol) in formamide (20 mL), the mixture was put into microwave reactor to react under a power of 400 W for 1 h at 110 °C. The mixture was then filtered and washed with brine. The filtrate was extracted by ethyl acetate and organic layer was collected. After concentration followed by recrystallization in ethyl acetate, compound 5 of white solid was obtained (0.2 g, 50%). ESI-MS m/z : 295.3 $[M+H]^+$, 317.3 $[M+Na]^+$. 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 12.17 (s, 1H), 8.04 (s, 1H), 7.51 (s, 1H), 7.09 (s, 1H), 4.36-4.14 (m, 4H), 3.83 (s, 4H), 3.45 (d, $J = 0.7$ Hz, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 162.39, 154.74, 148.62, 145.33, 142.76, 115.65, 109.06, 106.47, 70.63, 70.48, 68.50, 68.43, 59.27, 59.23.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Commonly, quinazolinone was produced from substituted benzonitrile through a scheme of at least two steps^{14,15}, and the yield ranged 8%~30%^{10,11,16}. We firstly used this process (**Scheme 2**) to synthesize compound 5. Briefly, the three steps of this reaction needed 13 hours to finish, including reduction of nitrated benzonitrile intermediate to give aminated benzonitrile one, then converting of cyano group into an amide group and finally formation of quinazolinone ring by conventional Niementowski cyclization¹⁵. The results showed that the yield of heterocyclization of quinazolinone ring was 29.8%, which was similarly low as those reported¹⁶ and would lead a low overall yield thereafter. In conclusion, this reaction route was somewhat complicated and time-consuming.

Scheme 2. Reagents and conditions: (a) ammonium formate, 5% Pd/C, 77°C, 2 h; (b) K₂CO₃, DMSO, 30% H₂O₂, 0°C to rt. 1 h; (c) Formamid, formic acid, r.t. to 100°C, 10 h.

There have been many researchers dedicating to optimize the reaction route and improve the yield of quinazolinone intermediate. Kundu *et al.*¹² synthesized some antitumor quinazolinone precursors by one-pot reductive cyclization method intending to increase the yield of heterocyclization. The structure and corresponding yield of the investigated quinazolinone derivatives were listed in **Fig. 2**. As shown in **Fig. 2**, when there were no substituents at the meta and para positions on the benzene ring, the yield of the cyclization reaction was the highest about 90%. When there was substituent at meta position, the synthesis yield of quinazolinone was reduced. However, the reaction lasted at least five hours at 150 °C. In another study of synthesizing quinazolinone intermediates for developing cannabinoid receptor agonists, Raimo Saari *et al.*¹³ successfully produced quinazolin-4(3*H*)-one using 2-aminobenzonitrile as starting material by microwave-assisted reaction (100 °C) within 5 minutes and got a yield of 64%. Besides, Li Feng *et al.*,¹⁷ also developed a method to yield compound 5 by microwave reaction using substituted aminobenzamide as starting material. The heterocyclization was realized in the presence of iridium complex and ambient of N₂ within 2 hours at 120 °C, and the yield of cyclization was 85%. However, this reaction was just the last step of the commonly used three-step scheme for synthesis of compound 5. The results encouraged us to figure out whether the one-pot microwave reaction could improve the synthesis of compound 5.

Entry	Substrate	R ¹	R ²	R ³	Product	Yield%
1	1a	H	H	H	2a	89
2	1b	OMe	OBn	H	2b	87
3	1c	OBn	OMe	H	2c	83
4	1d	OMe	OMe	H	2d	78
5	1e	OMe	H	OMe	2e	71
6	1f	OMe	OMe	OMe	2f	75
7	1g	Cl	H	H	2g	79
8	1h	SMe	H	H	2h	73

Figure 2 The structure and yield of quinazolinone derivatives prepared by one-pot reductive cyclization reported by Kundu *et al.*¹².

Five different conditions of microwave reaction were investigated in this work. The effect of microwave power, temperature and time of reaction on the yield of compound 5 was listed in **Table 1**. The results showed that the combination of high microwave power or/and reaction temperature and long reacting time were unfavorable to the synthesis, which yield no or just a

bit of product. When using moderate power, reaction temperature and time, the yield of 50% was achieved, which was 1.68 folds as much as that got by the commonly used three-step synthetic scheme. More significantly, only one step was needed to produce quinazolinone derivatives from substituted nitrobenzotrile in 1 hour, making the synthesis friendlier.

Table 1 Results of condition screening of microwave reaction in synthesis of 6,7-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)quinazolin-4(3H)-one.

Entry	Power	Temperature	Time	Yield
1	800W	120°C	10min	No product
2	400W	120°C	60min	No product
3	800W	200°C	2min	Trace product
4	400W	200°C	60min	8.4%
5	400W	110°C	60min	50%

CONCLUSIONS

In our study, compound 5, the important intermediate in synthesis of erlotinib analogues, was successfully produced by using an easy one-pot microwave reaction from starting material of substituted nitrobenzotrile. and the reaction time was only one thirteenth of the commonly used three-step synthetic scheme. Although the two substituents on benzene ring of the starting material were somewhat bulky, a relatively satisfactory yield was achieved under appropriated reaction condition, which would further ensure an acceptable overall yield of erlotinib analogues designed. Therefore, the results of this work may give valuable reference to synthesis of other quinazolinone derivatives of different substituents.

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